

A Race for Votes: White Privilege in Toronto Politics

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THE JANUARY 21, 2014 APPEARANCE of a video of Toronto Mayor Rob Ford drunk and out on the town was but the latest example of the mayor's repeated displays of tomfoolery. The video entitled "Rob Ford Speaking in Drunk Jamaican Patois Accent at Steak Queen Restaurant" was posted on YouTube and the story was quickly picked up by the Canadian and international press including *The Toronto Star* and *The New York Times*. Both the city of Toronto and Canada as a whole have undergone significant cultural shifts in the last forty years and the election of Ford is but one indication of the changes afoot in Canada's largest city.

Ford is an alcoholic and drug user, facts that were not widely known at the time of his election but that have come to light in the past year. He is also the son of millionaires. He has done a lot to obscure the fact of his wealth in order to gain the support of immigrants (recent and not so recent) and conservative-leaning working class people—many of whom voted for him because he promised to cut their taxes and extend public transportation in their neighborhoods (mainly the outskirts of the city). That said, I do not think his election should be pinned exclusively on immigrants, people of colour, and the working class. While the demographics of the city have changed, the face of municipal politics has remained comparably white and/or wealthy. Ford is a product of the old boys' club and he would not be where he is today without the support of very powerful people. He is so emboldened that he insists he will not step down as mayor and that he will in fact run again even after lying about, and then admitting to, smoking crack cocaine. These actions reek of white privilege. Which brings us to this question: With all that white privilege, what is Ford doing at Steak Queen cussing in Jamaican patois?

While it seems the video was initially leaked to shame Ford (by all accounts an emotion he is incapable of experiencing), I think those behind the leaks misunderstand the way in which Ford uses his “common man” image to consolidate power. While some may think that these videos prove that Ford is unfit for office, he uses the aftermath of the leaks to suggest that the mainstream media is picking on him and to further represent himself as a marginalized figure in Toronto politics. And who better to represent the marginalized of Toronto than someone who is on the margins themselves? The problem with this equation is that Ford, a wealthy, middle-aged white man elected to public office, is not a marginalized person. For him to suggest that he is, in any way, part of Toronto’s underclass is to condescend to immigrants and people of colour in the city he represents.

Ford’s use of patois is insulting to Caribbean-Canadians. It is problematic because in the video he switches codes between Standard English and patois in order to express his oppositional relationship to the Toronto Police Department. In this context he deploys patois to signal his solidarity with black Canadians, a population that has historically faced racial profiling and harassment by police. Ford was not being followed by the police because of his racial identity, however, but because police had noticed his repeated interactions with known criminals including drug dealers. They had reason to suspect that he might be involved in criminal activities himself—such as the possession of illegal drugs. This is one of the reasons his use of patois is derisive, because he is seeking to downplay his white privilege to identify with a black experience for which he has no real knowledge or access. His interactions with the police had nothing to do with racial profiling and Toronto Police had every reason to be investigating Ford. The issue of Ford’s disrespect of immigrant communities is one even deeper, however, than racial appropriation.

The working class and immigrant populations in Toronto are hugely diverse and in this milieu Jamaican patois indexes something (and not necessarily the same “something”) not only to Caribbean people but also to other minorities in the city. It is equivalent to having a non-standard English accent. For many Canadians hearing or having an accent is less about specific national origins (Jamaica, the Philippines, etc.) and more about the idea of being “newly arrived.” This is not to say that all new immigrants to Canada have accents or that some Canadians do not maintain their “foreign” accents even after living in Canada for decades. What I am suggesting, rather, is that having others notice or respond to your accent in ways that make you feel socially and culturally marginal is a common experience for immigrants in Toronto. At the same time the high rate of immigration to Toronto in recent decades has meant that different languages and accents are increasingly present throughout the city.

As a result of the large Caribbean immigrant population, patois has been a part of the city's diverse identity for some time now. Take, for example, Toronto rapper Kardinal Offishall's 2010 single "The Anthem," a patriotic ode to the city that opens with the claim that Toronto is "home to the blocko, patois and proper English" (Harrow 2010). Throughout the song Kardinal reps the same black, immigrant, and working class neighbourhoods that Ford claims to be down with during his patois rant. These neighbourhoods include Regent Park, Malvern, and Rexdale. Kardinal describes Toronto as a place where Italians and Filipinos share space with people from Africa and the Caribbean—he calls out "Trinis" and "Yardies" from his parents' native Jamaica, in particular (Harrow 2010). Kardinal's Toronto is multiethnic, multiracial, and attentive to class differences. His second verse notes that the city is populated by "immigrants from long distances/working class people/and some others with some privileges" (Harrow 2010). The song rightly acknowledges that any conversation about race and immigration in Toronto must take into account class. While Kardinal references the intersectionality of race and class, Ford seems to collapse the two, unable to imagine a more complex relationship between race and class identities in Toronto.

Ford's oppositional stance toward Toronto Police is in keeping with the image he has created for himself as an anti-establishment figure. He uses this image to bolster his "street cred" with immigrants and people of colour many of whom are forced to occupy social, cultural, and political space outside of mainstream Canadian culture. Ford misses, however, precisely what Kardinal has deftly identified in his lyrics—that is social, cultural, and economic diversity *within* black, brown, and immigrant populations. Does Ford know that there are many black and brown people who *do not* cuss like him? What about the immigrants who are more interested in job creation, educational opportunities, and owning their own businesses than street credibility?

Looking more closely at Ford's use of patois, it is important to consider the actual words he uses. Jamaicans across class boundaries, for example, often avoid the use of the word "bumbaclot" because it is not deemed respectable. In other words there are a lot of Jamaican-Canadians that he is *not* speaking to when he uses that language. Ford's use of "bumbaclot" and "raasclot" go beyond racial appropriation when considered alongside some of his other scandalous utterances. Along with his references to "eating pussy" and "drunken stupors," his use of Jamaican patois can be read as a performative refusal of the politics of respectability and extreme politeness that typify Canadian culture. This refusal of respectability is the only way in which Ford could be said to work outside of the Canadian political establishment. He is simply in office to get the job done, he tells Torontonians. So no one should worry if he smokes crack, cusses in public, or socializes with drug dealers because he is still a competent mayor, and one that is looking

out for those on the margins of society as opposed to hobnobbing with the upper classes. The people of Toronto would do well to consider, however, that Ford's refusal of respectability is indeed a *performance*. He can embody this performance when it is convenient for him because of the race, class and gender privilege that he claims at the same time as he is mimicking Jamaican dons. Ford can speak patois whenever he wants to but he is still the rich, white kid from Etobicoke.

It seems as if it is specifically his penchant for polyvocality and his complicated relationship with the Toronto Police Department that increases his appeal with certain constituents. He is embarrassing. But some voters in Toronto find something to identify with in that. Watching Toronto television news recently I noticed people of diverse racial backgrounds interviewed who continue to support Ford because they think he is "like one of us." His coarseness is chalked up to "plain-speaking" or honesty. In the video at the Steak Queen Ford tells the other customers, "I don't bullshit. I'm a straight up guy." He also suggests that no other politicians are willing to venture to the underserved neighbourhoods that he takes an interest in such as James-town, Malvern and Jane and Finch. While every Torontonians is entitled to their opinion and their vote I think it is also fair that they expect more than lip service from their politicians.

In the music video that accompanies Kardinal's "Anthem," the rapper is seen interacting with Torontonians from various walks of life all over the city. He includes clips from Yonge and Dundas (the center of Toronto's downtown core), the Beaches (an upper middle class enclave), St. Lawrence Market (a neighbourhood that prides itself on offering mixed-income housing), Little Italy, and the nightclub district on Richmond Street. There are also images of a Jewish temple, an Islamic mosque, various universities and colleges, and landmarks of Toronto's cultural scene including the Art Gallery of Ontario, the Royal Ontario Museum, the Canadian Broadcasting Centre, and the Rogers Centre. "Any way you look at it we're seeing past differences. Yo! I am multi-culture," Kardinal raps as scenes from the city are presented in a rapid montage. Kardinal was raised in the rough and tumble Flemingdon Park but his vision of his hometown is expansive and inclusive of the city's diversity.

In the space of a four-minute song and video Kardinal does more to accurately represent the depth and diversity of Toronto than Rob Ford has done during his entire tenure as the city's mayor. Kardinal's music comes out of a tradition of Black Canadian culture and thought that is polyvocal and anti-racist at its core. I am struck at how closely Kardinal's work resonates with that of Trinidadian-Canadian writer and Toronto resident Dionne Brand. "In Toronto I live in the semi-detached, old new-immigrant houses where Italians, Chinese, Blacks, Koreans, South Asians and Portuguese make a rough peace," Brand writes in her 1994 essay collection *Bread Out of*

Stone: Recollections, Sex, Recognitions, Race, Dreaming, Politics (Brand 1994, 9). It is Brand's project to interrogate the image of the multicultural Canadian mosaic and to place critical pressure on that image to highlight the racial, class, and gender inequalities that still plague Canadian society. At the same time her body of work, like Kardinal's "Anthem," can be read as homage to the various immigrant groups that make Toronto a world-class city. It is specifically because of the rich contribution that immigrants make to the city of Toronto that they must be wary of politicians like Ford who uses his platform and privilege to ventriloquize for underrepresented communities. If there is anything to be learned from Ford, and the debacle that has been his tenure as mayor, it is that there is a large gap waiting to be filled in terms of the political representation of immigrants and people of colour in Toronto. Perhaps if Ford really cared about Jamestown and Jane and Finch he would stop trying to speak for these communities and instead focus on creating forums which would effectively allow them to speak for themselves and to be heard.

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